

**HOW TO RAISE MULTILINGUAL CHILDREN?
- THE MOST APPROPRIATE AGE FOR STARTING SPEAKING
CHILDREN IN MULTIPLE LANGUAGES AS WELL AS STRATEGIES
(PERIOD 0 TO 3)**

Habibova Shahnoza Keldiyor qizi

shahnozahabibova6@gmail.com

Navoi State Pedagogical Institute
English language and literature faculty student

Usmonova Dilnoza Ulug‘bek qizi

joxa.ibragimov777@gmail.com

Navoi State Pedagogical Institute
English language and literature faculty student

Burkhanova Mamura Gulyamovna

scientific adviser

Abstract. Learning a new language has been becoming the most required ability since decades. Unlike the existing stereotype among nations that language acquisition from the infancy is challenging process and could lead to the complication of babies' brain, multilingualism can help them develop intellectually, socially and economically. Particularly, one can learn multiple languages through taking advantage of following strategies.

Key words: multilingual children, memory capacity, bilingual, mass knowledge, zero to third period.

Introduction. Since the advancements of technology made it possible to digitalize workplaces at an alarming rate, the requirements for language skills are increasing as well. If intellectual, economic and social benefits of this phenomenon are taken into account, the capacity of speaking more than one language might provide the opportunity of getting access to different life domains ranging from job promotion to networking skills which is provoking the actuality of raising multilingual children. Rather than learning new vocabulary, creating that language environment through helping the children use these words in their daily lives at an earlier age raise the probability of their speaking in that targeted language.

On the other hand, most parents claim that, exposure to foreign languages at previous stages of life might be challenging for young learners in terms of their memory capacity, however, recent studies contradict these beliefs mentioned above. This thesis will briefly discuss the most appropriate age for starting children in a different language as well as providing strategies.

Methods of analysis. It's common knowledge that, teaching a new language to a baby should be started as soon as they have improved their speaking which means that they have no enough capability to differentiate languages. What's more, other parents claim that it doesn't matter whether children are challenged to learn new language or not, they have no any concept about it until they developed their speaking skills. But the Japanese scientist Masaru Ibuka wrote in his book that it is too late to develop children's abilities after the age of three. His book "Kindergarten is too late tells the story of teacher Masao Nagata. He quits his job and devotes his life to the education of his children. At the same time, she started teaching English, Spanish, Italian, German, French and her mother tongue to her two-and-a-half-year-old son and three-month-old daughter. Masao Nagata says that his children are not confused about learning five languages at the same time. "We used to deal with foreign languages only through the radio. These radio broadcasts were conducted by very polite presenters. Pronunciation exercises were repeated for a long time. "The children used to pronounce everything correctly when they spoke," he said. So it can be assumed that children have more superior abilities to receive information than old aged people. But we must not fear for "giving more something" or encouraging them to do something as their brain receives knowledge like paper absorbs the water, and we can say that it is never too early to start teaching children to speak multiple languages.

Discussion and conclusion. Recent investigations by linguistic experts suggest that zero to three is the best period for children to learn multiple languages when their mind is fresh enough to acquire mass knowledge. According to statistics, all languages of the world comprise around 800, while a sound used one language also exists in another 40 languages too. Regarding infants, they have well developed hearing skills even when they are foetus in womb and they are naturally gifted with differentiating those 800 sounds as well as understand. So, exposing to more than one language will not make them confused while teaching unborn baby multiple languages more effective than adult learners particularly with parental resources.

Moreover, there is another reason why zero to three is concerned as the most vital period for learning a language. The entire life of person is based on what we gained until we are at the age of three in which whatever you put to babies' mind it has effect on developing as a person. As a proof of this belief we might state this research taken

by Harvard University, children who experienced with more than one languages are highly likely to improve their creativity, critical thinking and intellectual skills which provides them with an opportunity to broaden their horizon.

So, how can we bring up multilingual and or bilingual children? There are following strategies:

A family where one partner has to choose one language and the other need to another language to make conversation with their children from birth. For example father speaks in English and mother speaks in France throughout interaction or whole family choose one new language as they do it with their children. When it comes to native language, children can develop it by surrounding environment including social circle. In this way, child has to keep that targeted language in order to talk with parents.

The first teacher your child has is you. You are your child's first teacher. It's best to start speaking to your child in more than 1 language as early as possible – that is, from birth. Some families decide it's better to introduce the second language only after the child speaks the first language well, at about ages 3 or 4. However, there is no evidence that this helps the child to speak either language better.

Many children in North America and around the world grow up exposed to two languages from an early age. Parents of bilingual infants and toddlers have important questions about the costs and benefits of early bilingualism, and how to best support language acquisition in their children. Here, we separate common myths from scientific findings to answer six of parents' most common questions about early bilingual development.

Along with this, learning through songs could also work as effectively. Children are likely to keep things in their mind when they face with it in their daily life. Singing songs or watching films in a new language help children to speak.

Meanwhile, parents can use some storytelling methods. While telling night stories to their children they may say it in a new language in which parents can take advantage of visual materials including picture based text books. What about bilingual infants? Again, the research is clear: bilingual infants readily distinguish their two languages and show no evidence of confusion. Languages differ on many dimensions—even if you don't speak Russian or Mandarin, you can likely tell one from the other. Infants are also sensitive to these perceptual differences, and are particularly attuned to a language's rhythm. Infants can discriminate rhythmically dissimilar languages like English and French at birth (Byers-Heinlein, Burns, & Werker, 2010; Mehler et al., 1988), and by age 4 months they can tell even rhythmically similar languages like French and Spanish apart (Bosch & Sebastián-Gallés, 1997, 2001; Nazzi, 2000). Bilingual infants may be even more sensitive than monolinguals when it comes to

discriminating languages. Recent research has shown that 4-month-old monolingual and bilingual infants can discriminate silent talking faces speaking different languages (Weikum et al., 2007). However, by 8 months of age, only bilinguals are still sensitive to the distinction, while monolinguals stop paying attention to subtle variations in facial movements (Sebastián-Gallés, Albareda-Castellot, Weikum, & Werker, 2012; Weikum et al., 2007). Instead of being confused, it seems that bilingual infants are sensitive to information that distinguishes their languages.

One of the most important benefits of early bilingualism is often taken for granted: bilingual children will know multiple languages, which is important for travel, employment, speaking with members of one's extended family, maintaining a connection to family culture and history, and making friends from different backgrounds. However, beyond obvious linguistic benefits, researchers have investigated whether bilingualism confers other non-linguistic advantages (Akhtar & Menjivar, 2012).

Several studies have suggested that bilinguals show certain advantages when it comes to social understanding. In some ways, this is not surprising, as bilinguals must navigate a complex social world where different people have different language knowledge. For example, bilingual preschoolers seem to have somewhat better skills than monolinguals in understanding others' perspectives, thoughts, desires, and intentions (Bialystok & Senman, 2004; Goetz, 2003; Kovács, 2009). Young bilingual children also have enhanced sensitivity to certain features of communication such as tone of voice (Yow & Markman, 2011).

Bilinguals also show some cognitive advantages. In particular, bilinguals appear to perform a little bit better than monolinguals on tasks that involve switching between activities and inhibiting previously learned responses (Bialystok, Craik, & Luk, 2012). Although these advantages have been mostly studied in bilingual adults (Costa, Hernández, & Sebastián-Gallés, 2008) and children (Bialystok & Martin, 2004), new evidence suggests that even bilingual infants (Kovács & Mehler, 2009a, 2009b) and toddlers (Poulin-Dubois, Blaye, Coutya, & Bialystok, 2011) show cognitive advantages. Additionally, there is some evidence that bilingual infants are advantaged in certain aspects of memory, for example generalizing information from one event to a later event (Brito & Barr, 2012).

LEARNing landscapes

However, parents should not lose hope if they have not exposed their children to each language from birth. Infants' brains and learning environments are special and non-recreatable, but there are many other ways to foster bilingual development. Here we overview two possibilities. First, some parents (particularly those who can afford childcare) choose to hire bilingual nannies or send children to bilingual preschools, in

order to maximize their children's exposure to another language. This can certainly result in increased bilingual proficiency, but it is essential to provide continued opportunities to practice each language once the child is older. Parental expectations should be quite low if children do not have opportunities to continue learning and using a language throughout development. However, keep in mind that bilingual exposure does not necessarily translate to being a bilingual who is able to understand and speak a language fluently. Researchers generally consider a child to be bilingual if he or she receives at least 10–25% of exposure to each language (Byers-Heinlein, under review; Place & Hoff, 2011; Marchman et al., 2010; Marchman, Martínez-Sussmann, & Dale, 2004), but this level of exposure by no means guarantees functional bilingualism (De Houwer, 2007).

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